

Stability Constants of Zinc-, Cadmium- and Manganese(II) Complexes of 1-Amidino-*O*-isobutylurea

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In continuation of our study on 1-amidino-*O*-alkylurea complexes with some transition metal ions, we report here the stability constants of the complexes of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Mn^{II} with 1-amidino-*o*-isobutylurea (ABⁱUH) in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths and temperatures using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The values of thermodynamic stability constants have been evaluated¹.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were determined by Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique². The protonation constants ($\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$) of ligand were obtained from the formation curves of the proton-ligand system by plotting \bar{n}_A vs pH. Using the pH-titration curves, the values of \bar{n}_A (average number of protons bound to the ligand), \bar{n} (average number of ligands attached per metal ion) and pL (free-ligand exponent) were calculated. Metal-ligand formation constants of complexes ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) were calculated (Table 1) from the plots of \bar{n} vs pL corresponding to $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respec-

tively. Thermodynamic stability constants have been obtained by extrapolation of measured formation constants of zero ionic strength from graph between log of stability constants vs square-root of ionic strength. Stability constant gradually decreases with the increase of ionic strength and temperatures. Low temperature is favourable for complexation. The $\log K_1$ value for each of the metal complex is less than its $\log K_2$ value. The overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) of the metal chelates follow the trend : Zn > Mn > Cd.

Experimental

1-Amidino-*O*-isobutylurea (ABⁱUH) was reported earlier³. The pH-titrations of ABⁱUH and its complexes were carried out with KOH solution using a 111-E (Electronics India) pH meter at 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 *M* and at 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40°. A 1 *M* KNO₃ solution was used to control the ionic strength during the titrations. A 0.14 *M* KOH solution was prepared (free from carbonate) and standardised volumetrically. A 4 × 10⁻³ *M* HNO₃ solution was prepared by diluting the acid with CO₂-free water and

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF 1-AMIDINO-*O*-ISOBUTYLUREA AND OVERALL METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS AND TEMPERATURES

Cation	log K_n^H or log K_n	20°					$\mu = 0.01 M$			
		$\mu = 0.00$	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20 <i>M</i>	25°	30°	35°	40°
H ⁺	log K_1^H	—	12.10	12.00	11.90	11.75	11.95	11.85	11.70	11.60
	log K_2^H	—	12.20	11.00	10.80	10.60	10.90	10.70	10.60	10.50
	log β^H	—	23.30	23.00	22.70	22.85	22.85	22.50	22.30	22.10
Zn ^{II}	log K_1	9.70	9.20	9.00	8.80	8.60	9.00	8.90	8.50	7.90
	log K_2	3.95	3.60	3.50	3.40	3.30	3.40	3.30	3.50	3.40
	log β	13.65	12.80	12.50	11.20	11.90	12.40	12.20	12.00	11.30
Cd ^{II}	log K_1	6.30	5.70	5.50	5.30	5.20	5.40	5.30	5.20	5.00
	log K_2	3.70	3.20	3.15	3.10	3.00	3.15	3.15	3.10	3.10
	log β	10.00	8.90	8.65	8.40	8.20	8.55	8.45	8.30	8.10
Mn ^{II}	log K_1	6.60	5.90	5.60	5.30	5.20	5.50	5.40	5.30	5.25
	log K_2	3.75	3.45	3.30	3.25	3.20	3.20	3.15	3.10	3.00
	log β	10.35	9.35	8.90	8.55	8.40	8.70	8.55	8.40	8.2

standardised. The following three mixtures were prepared (a) HNO_3 ($4 \times 10^{-3} M$) + KNO_3 , (b) HNO_3 ($4 \times 10^{-3} M$) + KNO_3 + ligand ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) and (c) HNO_3 ($4 \times 10^{-3} M$) + KNO_3 + ligand ($3 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal ions ($6 \times 10^{-4} M$). The total volume in all the mixtures was adjusted to 25 ml with double-distilled water. These solutions were individually titrated against the standard KOH solution

References

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